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Reference document – Climate risk assessment
Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment of the
Region of Murcia (REGMURCIA CLIMAAX)
Spain, Region of Murcia

May 2025

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101093864. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document Information

Title	Phase 1 – Reference document
Brief Description	This Reference document provides the contextual basis, risk criteria and stakeholder framework to guide the REGMURCIA CLIMAAX project. It synthesises why droughts, floods and heatwaves are material climate risks for the Region of Murcia, outlines the available data landscape and governance context, and sets the principles for risk scoring and engagement.
Project name	Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment of the Region of Murcia (REGMURCIA CLIMAAX)
Country	Spain
Region/Municipality	Region of Murcia
Leading Institution	Regional Secretary of Energy, Sustainability and Climate Action (CARM)
Author(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salvador Gil-Guirado (Department of Geography, Universidad de Murcia, Murcia, Spain) • Pedro Jiménez-Guerrero (Department of Physics, Universidad de Murcia, Murcia, Spain) • Juan Pedro Montavez (Department of Physics, Universidad de Murcia, Murcia, Spain) • Alfredo Pérez-Morales (Department of Geography, Universidad de Murcia, Murcia, Spain)

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
AEMET	Agencia Estatal de Meteorología
CARM	Autonomous Community of the Region of Murcia
CEDEX	Center for Hydrographic Studies
CHS	Segura Hydrographic Confederation
CRA	Climate Risk Assessment
CREM	Regional Statistics Centre of Murcia
EEA	European Environment Agency
ERMACC	Estrategia Regional de Mitigación y Adaptación al Cambio Climático de la Región de Murcia
GVA	Gross Value Added
INE	Spanish National Statistics Institute
MITECO	Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge
PNACC	National Climate Change Adaptation Plan
RP	Return Period
SLR	Sea Level Rise
SNCZI	National Flood Hazard Mapping System
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
UMU	University of Murcia

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The Region of Murcia, located in the southeast of the Iberian Peninsula, is a Mediterranean region characterized by strong geographical contrasts, including coastal areas, inland basins, and mountain ranges. It covers an area of approximately 11,300 km² and has a population of around 1.5 million inhabitants. The region's economy relies heavily on agriculture, agri-food industry, tourism, and increasingly on renewable energy and logistics, which makes it particularly sensitive to climate-related impacts on water availability, coastal integrity, and infrastructure resilience.

Murcia is one of the most arid regions in Europe, with a semi-arid Mediterranean climate marked by high interannual variability in precipitation and frequent episodes of drought. However, the most critical natural risks affecting the region are hydrometeorological hazards, particularly flash floods, prolonged droughts, and heatwaves. These hazards have increased in frequency and intensity in recent decades due to climate change and growing urban pressure on flood-prone areas.

The region's topography, land use patterns, and urban development, often in hazard-prone areas, amplify the exposure and vulnerability of the population and economic activities. Furthermore, the combination of climate hazards with social vulnerability, such as aging populations in rural municipalities or unregulated urban expansion, increases the systemic risk.

At the sectoral level, the CARM economy presents the classic distribution of a developed and tertiary economy. However, the peculiarities of its economic structure, together with its geographic endowment, make the CARM economy and society especially vulnerable to climate risks, especially river and coastal flooding, heatwaves, and droughts. Four key economic subsectors are crucial in this regard: agriculture, tourism, trade, and transport.

According to the Gross Value Added (GVA) by sector of economic activity ([Figure 1-1](#)), of the €36,814,662 GVA in the CARM in 2023, 69% comes from the services sector. Compared to the national average of 75%, this reflects a lower tertiary sector in the CARM compared to the national average. This gap is due to the greater weight of regional agriculture and industry. In the case of agriculture, the regional figures are almost double the national figure (4.6% of regional GVA, compared to 2.7% nationally).

However, it is necessary to examine the underlying differences to understand the specificity of the regional economy. Thus, of the total GVA of the industrial sector in the CARM, 24% corresponds to the food industry, a sector directly linked to activities related to the agricultural model. Similarly, of the more than 1.2 million motor vehicles in the CARM in 2023, more than 12% were trucks and vans. These figures are much higher than the national average and highlight another highly specialized regional sector, indirectly related to agriculture: the transportation of agricultural products and goods. The composition of regional exports demonstrates this fact. Thus, in 2024, the CARM exported agricultural goods worth over €3.75 billion. These values represent 25.5% of the more than €14.2 billion exported. Similarly, in second place, with 21.3% (€3.036 billion) of the value of exports, are goods from the food industry. Thus, almost €7 billion of regional exports annually come directly or indirectly from agriculture. This reflects the economic and social importance of a sector highly vulnerable to climate change (CREM, 2025).

Figure 1-1 GVA by sector of economic activity in the CARM and Spain in 2023. Figure source: CREM, 2025.

The social and territorial relevance of agriculture is also reflected in other facts. More than 11% of employment and 14% of total unemployment in the CARM correspond to the agricultural sector. Values much higher than the percentage weight of the sectoral GVA, showing lower average incomes and a greater impact of unemployment in agriculture than in the rest of the sectors (Figure 1-2).

Figure 1-2 Employment and unemployment by economic sector in the CARM in the first quarter of 2025. Figure source: CREM, 2025.

On the other hand, the territorial, landscape, and environmental importance of agriculture is overwhelming. More than 31% of the CARM's surface area corresponds to cropland. Of this area, 45.8% corresponds to irrigated agriculture and the remaining 54.2% is dryland.

This duality also extends to crop types, with significant asymmetries in terms of production (in tons) and cultivated area (Figure 1-3). While almost two-thirds of the cultivated area corresponds to woody crops (almonds being particularly prominent, accounting for 26% of the cultivated area), production of this type of crop falls to 44% (almonds represent only 0.7% of production). Other significant cultivated areas correspond to olive groves, vineyards, cereals, citrus fruits, and vegetables. However, this does not correspond to production. While vegetables account for only 18% of the cultivated area, they represent almost half of the total production. This confirms the economic engine of agriculture for the regional economy. Something similar occurs with citrus fruit, with production exceeding its spatial representation. Quite the opposite of what occurs with cereals, olive

groves, and other types of production. These values reflect an asymmetrical agricultural system, with highly productive fruit and vegetable agriculture versus traditional, dryland agriculture, which has a significant spatial footprint but little direct economic impact.

Other key sectors with high vulnerability include transportation and the road network, directly affected by river and coastal flooding. Key sectors in the CARM include oil refining and the energy supply industry (11.3% of the regional GVA in 2023) and a value of refined oil exports exceeding €2.24 billion in 2024. These values depend on the Cartagena-Escombreras petrochemical hub, located on the regional coast, with the resulting vulnerability to coastal flooding.

Regional tourism deserves special mention, with an estimated contribution of more than 10.3% of regional GDP in 2024, still two percentage points below the Spanish average. The tourism sector is primarily driven by domestic tourists, 60% of whom stay in a secondary residence, mostly in coastal areas, during the summer (CES, 2025). This situation of high seasonality in the months of higher temperatures and in coastal areas poses a challenge for adaptation to climate change.

AGRICULTURAL AREA BY TYPE OF CROP

AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION BY TYPE OF CROP

Figure 1-3 Agricultural surface (top) and production (bottom) in the CARM according to crop type (Average 2019-2023). Figure source: [CREM](#), 2025.

1.2 Main objectives of REGMURCIA CLIMAAX project

REGMURCIA CLIMAAX will deliver a fully CLIMAAX-compliant Climate Risk Assessment for the Region of Murcia, ensuring scientific rigour, transparency and comparability with other European territories. The objectives that follow set out how the project will (1) quantify priority hazards; (2) pinpoint risk "hot-spots"; (3) prioritise action through participatory assessment; and (4) build the technical and governance capacity required for just and effective climate adaptation. These objectives can be summarised as:

- Conduct an Integrated Climate Risk Assessment (CRA) fully compliant with the five stages of the CLIMAAX Framework—Scoping, Risk Exploration, Risk Analysis, Key Risk Assessment, and Monitoring & Evaluation—for CARM.
- Quantify current and future risks for priority climate hazards in CARM. In this regard, the priority workflows implemented are droughts and river & coastal floods. Some information about heatwaves is also included.
- Locate spatial "hotspots" and sectoral vulnerabilities (irrigated fruit and vegetable farms, critical infrastructure, urban heat islands, tourism assets, and protected natural areas) to support evidence-based decision-making.
- Prioritize risk management through a participatory Key Risk Assessment, linking the results to the Regional Strategy for Mitigation and Adaptation to Climate Change of the Region of Murcia (ERMACC).
- Establish metrics, baselines and stakeholder commitments to enable the design of measures and the operationalisation of resilience mechanisms.
- Strengthen collaboration between public authorities, academia, and civil society, ensuring participatory governance and building lasting technical capacity.

The scoping links regional objectives (protect the agri-food sector, coastal economy and lifeline infrastructure, etc.) with governance levers (planning law, water and civil-protection mandates) and with the external programmes that can finance action.

With these objectives, REGMURCIA CLIMAAX is positioned as an essential catalyst for accelerating adaptation and resilience to climate change in one of the Mediterranean regions most affected by water stress and pressure on coastal ecosystems.

1.3 Project team

The team implementing REGMURCIA CLIMAAX combines the regulatory authority of the CARM with the scientific and technical excellence of the University of Murcia (UMU).

The CARM, through the Regional Secretary of Energy, Sustainability and Climate Action, assumes overall coordination, provides administrative data, and ensures the integration of results into the ERMACC, its legal framework, and other territorial management plans. UMU is responsible for the full application of the CLIMAAX methodology, the refinement of the assessment using high-resolution climate databases and GIS, advanced modeling of droughts, floods, and heatwaves, as well as the facilitation of technical meetings and the participatory process of the Key Risk Assessment.

The UMU team is made up of experts in Geography and Earth Physics with more than 200 JCR-Q1 publications and regularly collaborates with internationally renowned centers such as NCAR, ETH Zurich, and Yale University. It leverages proprietary tools (CLIMAX, SINQLAIR, COST, 4DROP) and a 1,008-CPU, 1 PB HPC cluster, ensuring rapid calculations and scientific traceability. This partnership

ensures a robust climate risk assessment aligned with European standards and backed by the institutional capacity necessary to update and transform it into concrete adaptation measures.

1.4 Scoping

The CRA for the Region of Murcia (CARM) aims to deliver a policy-ready, multi-hazard diagnosis—centred on agricultural droughts, river and coastal floods, and heatwaves—that quantifies hazard, exposure and vulnerability at actionable scales and translates findings into guidance for land-use, water and civil-protection decisions. The assessment is explicitly designed to feed high-level instruments (e.g., Spatial Plan/PORM, municipal general plans, climate-resilience bylaws) and to support investment programming (ERDF, LIFE, CAP eco-schemes, NextGen EU, private green finance). This regional scope and institutional anchorage ensure direct uptake by the administration with statutory powers over planning, water and emergency management.

Purpose and expected outcomes are threefold. First, to characterise how intensifying hazards intersect with CARM's economic base—irrigated market gardening and agri-food, coastal tourism, logistics and energy—thereby quantifying risks to GDP, jobs and ecosystem services. Second, to generate harmonised risk layers and curves that regulators can insert into territorial and sectoral plans. Third, to co-produce framework strategies and technical guidelines with risk owners and stakeholders through a two-tier engagement model (Risk-Ownership Committee and Consultation Panel).

2 Climate Risk Context

CARM's economy is heavily specialised in irrigated market gardening, the agri-food industry, coastal tourism, logistics and energy production. Extreme heat, increasing evapotranspiration and chronic water scarcity directly threaten this economic engine; coastal storm surges menace the Cartagena-Escombreras petrochemical hub and seasonally crowded beach tourism; flash floods disrupt a road network that already moves an above-average share of freight. Without an integrated risk-assessment the region risks mounting losses in GDP, employment and ecosystem services, undermining national food supply chains and EU single-market logistics (Table 2-1).

Table 2-1 Key economic sectors in CARM and expected climate impacts

Sector	Current weight	Principal climate stresses	Expected impact
Irrigated agriculture & agri-food	4.6 % of GVA; > 11 % employment	Chronic drought; heatwaves	Water-deficit yield loss, quality downgrades, higher cooling & fertigation costs
Coastal & cultural tourism	10.3 % GDP; highly seasonal	Heatwaves; coastal flooding; beach erosion	Thermal discomfort, loss of beach width, damage to second-home stock
Petro-chemical & energy hub	11.3 % GVA (oil refining, power)	Coastal surge; heat stress	Infrastructure downtime, safety hazards, supply-chain delays
Freight transport & logistics	12 % of vehicle fleet are trucks/vans	Fluvial floods; heatwaves	Road closures, higher maintenance & fuel consumption

2.1 Climate hazards in the CARM: assessment and management to date

The CARM has historically faced a variety of interrelated climate hazards, particularly intense in recent decades: extreme heatwaves, prolonged droughts, and both fluvial and coastal floods. These risks have been evaluated through scientific studies and civil protection plans and managed through reactive and preventive measures with varying degrees of effectiveness. In recent decades, the regional average temperature has increased by more than 2°C since 1981, and tropical nights (>20°C) have become more frequent (Espín-Sánchez, 2017). Regional health authorities, in coordination with the Ministry of Health, implement heatwave alert plans each summer, using a four-level warning system (green, yellow, orange, red) to protect vulnerable populations (elderly, children, sick people) (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2024). These campaigns include recommendations to avoid sun exposure, stay hydrated, and provide climate shelters.

Regarding droughts, CARM experiences structural water scarcity and a form of "chronic drought" due to its semi-arid Mediterranean climate. Historically, the region has addressed this issue through significant investment in water infrastructure. Since the 1980s, it has developed desalination plants and wastewater reuse systems, positioning Murcia as a national leader in reclaimed water usage (Pérez Morales et al., 2014). Currently, more than 90% of treated wastewater is reused, and drip irrigation is applied to about 90% of the farmland (Sala-Garrido, R., Molinos-Senante, M., Fuentes Pascual, R., Hernández-Sancho, 2020). These measures have helped avoid severe water restrictions even during intense droughts. However, challenges remain: illegal groundwater extraction and water losses due to insufficient maintenance continue to be problems (Simón and Oller, 2024). An integrated approach to reducing water footprints across sectors is still lacking, leaving the region vulnerable to increasingly intense droughts.

Fluvial floods are a historic risk in the CARM due to the torrential rainfall patterns of the Segura basin. Murcia has a Special Civil Protection Plan for Flood Risk (CARM and DGPC, 2007), which

identifies flood-prone areas and coordinates emergency responses. Despite this, high exposure persists: nearly 800 critical points (urban areas, dry streambeds, and agricultural lands) face severe flood risks under intense rainfall events (CHS, 2023). Past urban planning decisions have allowed construction in flood-prone areas, increasing vulnerability (Pérez-Morales et al., 2018). The floods caused by the 2019 DANA event severely impacted the region, resulting in seven fatalities and over €1.3 billion in damages (Romero-Díaz and Pérez-Morales, 2021). These events have led to strengthened emergency protocols and investments in drainage infrastructure. Coastal flooding, while less frequent to date, is emerging as a threat due to sea level rise (SLR) and intensified maritime storms. Several sections of the Murcian coast are projected to lose beaches in the coming years, impacting tourism and residential areas (CARM, 2019).

In summary, climate risks in Murcia have been partially assessed and managed through sectoral plans (health, water, emergency), but responses remain fragmented. The region has demonstrated both strengths (e.g., leadership in water adaptation) and weaknesses (e.g., inadequate urban planning, lack of integration between adaptation and land use). These challenges define the problem this project aims to address.

2.2 Problem addressed and broader context

The central issue targeted by this project is the CARM's growing vulnerability to climate change impacts, especially more frequent and intense heatwaves, droughts, and floods. These hazards already affect quality of life, economic productivity, and regional ecosystems (Calvin et al., 2023; IPCC, 2022). For instance, rising temperatures and heatwaves increase summer mortality and reduce labor productivity; chronic drought threatens irrigated agriculture, a key sector; and floods damage infrastructure, housing, and crops, causing significant economic losses.

The project operates within the broader regional and national development context. CARM plays a key role in agricultural exports, coastal tourism, and renewable energy. However, these development drivers are highly sensitive to natural resource availability and climate stability. Known as the "orchard of Europe," the region's agriculture depends on fertile soil and reliable water. Desertification is advancing rapidly, with the region losing up to 19 million tonnes of soil annually due to erosion (Eekhout et al., 2021). Projections show decreasing rainfall and rising temperatures, potentially leading to further land abandonment (Andrade et al., 2021).

Rapid and sometimes unregulated urbanization has increased exposure to climate risks. Cities like Murcia, Cartagena, and Lorca experience significant urban heat island effects due to limited greenery and extensive pavement (Gómez et al., 2023). Construction in flood-prone areas has placed thousands of homes at risk: around 17% of homes in the region are located in flood hazard zones (Cánovas-García and Vargas Molina, 2024). At the national level, CARM shares similar vulnerabilities with other Mediterranean regions (e.g., Andalusia, Valencia), aligning the project with Spain's broader climate adaptation priorities and the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan (PNACC) (MITECO, 2020).

2.3 Governance context for climate risk assessment

CARM's climate governance has evolved in recent years, establishing institutional and regulatory frameworks for climate risk assessment and adaptation. In 2020, the regional government declared a Climate and Environmental Emergency and adopted the Regional Strategy for Mitigation and Adaptation to Climate Change of the Region of Murcia (ERMACC) (CARM, 2019). The strategy sets out 15 action lines, including integrating adaptation into territorial and urban planning, protecting the

coastline from SLR, strengthening public health responses to heat, and supporting local adaptation through the Covenant of Mayors.

The Regional Observatory for Climate Change acts as a participatory body involving scientists, government agencies (including AEMET, the CHS Authority, Coastal Authority), businesses, and civil society (AdapteCCa, 2025). This observatory channels scientific knowledge into policy and monitors the progress of regional strategy. Within the administration, the Environmental Promotion and Climate Change Service coordinates adaptation implementation.

Murcia complies with national and international frameworks, including Spain's Climate Change Law and the EU Floods Directive. The region's flood risk management aligns with national civil protection and the CHS (CARM and DGPC, 2007) flood plans. On drought management, the Segura Basin's Special Drought Plan outlines indicators and actions that Murcia implements in coordination with users. The region mobilizes its own budget and European funds (e.g., ERDF, Next Generation EU) to support resilience investments. Despite this, studies highlight shortcomings in implementation, including gaps in integrating adaptation into all urban and water planning instruments and a lack of interdepartmental coordination.

2.4 External influences and synergies

The Climate-Risk Assessment will be embedded in—and benefit from—several external initiatives. It will adopt the methodological benchmarks and forthcoming “regional resilience contracts” of the [EU Mission on Adaptation](#), draw on transferable tools for urban drainage, drought management and stakeholder engagement developed by [LIFE-ADAPTATE](#) and [Interreg NEXT MED](#), and serve as the technical reference for investment decisions foreseen in the Segura River Basin Management Plan 2022-27 (CHS, 2023) and the [REPowerEU solar-irrigation programme](#). This alignment ensures consistency with EU policy, unlocks complementary funding streams, and accelerates the uptake of best practice in CARM.

2.5 Strategic scope of CLIMAAX_REGMURCIA

A distinguishing feature of CLIMAAX_REGMURCIA is its regional scale and institutional anchorage. Unlike many CRA pilots focused on a single municipality or catchment, this assessment spans the entire territory of the Region of Murcia, applying several CLIMAAX workflow—drought, heat-wave and fluvial and coastal flood—within a single, integrated frame. Because the project is steered by the regional administration, which holds legal competence over land-use planning, civil protection and water management, its outputs will feed directly into high-level instruments such as the Spatial Plan (PORM), municipal general plans and forthcoming climate-resilience bylaws. Rather than prescribing isolated “hard” measures, the CRA will generate framework strategies, technical guidelines and, where necessary, proposals for regulatory amendments that enable local authorities, businesses, farmer cooperatives and civil-society organisations to mainstream adaptation in their decisions. It will also map the financing landscape—ERDF, LIFE, CAP eco-schemes, Next-Generation-EU, private green bonds—so that priority actions identified by the assessment can move rapidly from concept to funded implementation.

2.6 Participation and risk ownership

The CLIMAAX-REGMURCIA participation plan is organised in two concentric tiers so that those who own the risk can work continuously with a wider community of information users, vulnerable groups and external experts.

- Tier 1 – Risk-Ownership Committee (mandatory semi-structured interviews). This tier circle comprises:
 - regional line departments with statutory competence for water management, civil protection, spatial planning, public health and agriculture;
 - the river-basin management authority.
 - the national meteorological service.
 - public and private operators of critical transport-logistics and energy infrastructure.
 - leading research universities and applied research centres.
 - most widely established environmental NGOs.
 - apex business organisations representing agriculture, industry, commerce and tourism.

Members of this committee will validate the analytical methods and review interim findings through one-to-one interviews and ad-hoc technical meetings.

- Tier 2 – Consultation Panel (survey / Delphi).

The outer circle brings together local governments, professional institutes, environmental and neighbourhood NGOs, chambers of commerce and transport associations. These stakeholders will be engaged mainly via an online questionnaire and a two-round Delphi exercise to comment on exposure maps, acceptable-risk levels and draft adaptation guidelines, complemented by webinars and sector-specific co-creation sessions.

3 Preliminary Risk Exploration

The Region of Murcia, located in one of the most arid areas of Europe, is particularly vulnerable to three climate-related hazards: fluvial and coastal floods, droughts and heatwaves. These risks are not only expected to intensify under future climate change scenarios, but they are already producing significant socio-economic and environmental impacts today. Therefore, the decision to focus on floods and droughts responds to three criteria:

1. High historical impact (e.g., deaths, damage, emergency declarations).
2. Increasing exposure and vulnerability due to urbanization, tourism pressure, and agricultural practices.
3. Strategic importance of the affected sectors (e.g., agriculture, housing, health, energy) for regional resilience and economic stability.

Additionally, these hazards are interconnected: droughts and heatwaves amplify wildfire risk and water-system stress, while floods and droughts represent opposite expressions of the same hydrological variability spectrum.

3.1 Current situation of drought risk in the CARM

Regarding drought and aridity these are critical issues in the CARM, a traditionally agricultural area highly sensitive to water scarcity. Although historically addressed through storage and irrigation infrastructure—dubbed the “Murcian miracle”—current strategies are proving insufficient in a climate change context (Chazarra-Zapata et al., 2020; Grindlay et al., 2011). Repeated and severe droughts, along with rising temperatures, signal a transition from semi-arid to arid conditions, posing significant risks to sustainable socio-economic development and accelerating desertification (Andrade et al., 2021; Beguería et al., 2025).

CARM has one of Europe’s driest climates, especially along its southern coast, with annual precipitation barely exceeding 270 mm. Climate indices based on 20th-century data classify most of the region as semi-arid, but recent decades show a sharp decline in rainfall and a marked increase in evapotranspiration, shifting large areas into arid classification (Martínez-Valderrama, 2024).

Meteorological droughts—defined by long periods of below-average precipitation—have historically affected Murcia. Since 1963, at least eleven major drought events have been recorded, with the 2023–24 drought exhibiting rainfall levels under 50 mm in most of the region. Indicators like SPI, SPEI, and PDSI show rising frequency and severity of extreme dry spells (Gil-Guirado and Pérez-Morales, 2024), consistent with patterns across the Mediterranean basin under climate change scenarios (Sousa et al., 2011; Spinoni et al., 2018). In the case of the longest precipitation time series in the Region of Murcia (CARM), corresponding to the city of Murcia, a considerable increase in the duration of dry periods has been observed from 1863 to the present. During this time, average annual precipitation has decreased by approximately 90 mm, with the most pronounced reductions occurring in autumn and spring—seasons typically associated with the highest rainfall and closely linked to the rainfed agricultural production cycle in the region (Gil-Guirado and Pérez-Morales, 2019). As illustrated in [Figure 3-1](#), the spatial patterns of the 1970 and 1981–1984 drought periods show that southeastern Spain—particularly the CARM—experienced intense and persistent rainfall deficits. These extreme events were characterized by annual precipitation below 200 mm and anomalies exceeding –50% in key agricultural areas. The duration and spatial extent of these deficits

underscore the region’s high sensitivity to climate variability and the urgent need to implement robust adaptation strategies.

Figure 3-1 Observed Spatial Patterns and Anomalies of Precipitation in Spain During Historical Drought Periods (1970 and 1981–1984). Source: Serrano-Notivol et al., 2017.

Hydrological droughts—when reservoir and groundwater levels drop below normal—are increasingly common, especially as climate change affects both local rainfall and water transfers like the Tajo-Segura aqueduct. The Segura basin currently has Spain’s lowest reservoir levels (17% in Sept 2024; MITECO, 2024). Though previously mitigated by inter-basin transfers, more frequent and intense droughts are causing operational interruptions and greater reliance on aquifers, risking long-term hydrological imbalance (Torelló-Sentelles and Franzke, 2022).

Despite a recent exceptionally wet spring in the Segura River Basin District (CHS), current water reserves in the Segura basin remain among the lowest in the country. As of the last week of April 2025, reservoir storage stood at 31.4% of total capacity (MITECO, 2025a). While this figure does not represent a historical minimum, it reflects a persistent pattern: both currently and historically, the Segura basin consistently registers the lowest water availability among all river basins in Spain. Out of a total capacity of 1,140 hm³ across CHS reservoirs, only 358 hm³ are currently available for agricultural, industrial, and domestic use—excluding environmental flow requirements. The strong dependency of the Region of Murcia’s (CARM) agricultural and socioeconomic systems on these limited water resources highlights the region’s structural vulnerability to hydrological stress.

Agricultural droughts, exacerbated by high evaporative demand, increasingly threaten crop yields. Studies project substantial yield reductions under prolonged water stress (Karrou and Oweis, 2012), particularly in light soils with low water retention. Phenological changes and soil degradation further compromise agricultural sustainability (Peña-Gallardo et al., 2019).

The Copernicus Interactive Climate Atlas highlights a marked escalation across the three core drought dimensions considered in the CLIMAAX Drought & Water Scarcity workflow. In the Segura River Basin, projections for 2041–2070 indicate a substantial increase in Consecutive Dry Days (CDD), with durations extending by 5–10 days per year under SSP2-4.5 and by 12–18 days under SSP5-8.5. At the same time, the SPEI-12 index trends increasingly negative, pointing to longer, more persistent meteorological droughts. When translated into hydrological terms, these changes reduce the recurrence interval of critical reservoir inflow shortages, representing a significant escalation in drought hazard. In the CARM, where 46% of cultivated land relies on irrigation and agri-food exports exceed €6.9 billion annually, such intensification collides with extreme exposure: high-value, water-intensive crops, rapid urban expansion dependent on desalinated water, and a dense agro-industrial network responsible for a quarter of regional exports. This exposure is further amplified by systemic vulnerabilities, including ageing farming populations, economically fragile smallholders, and aquifers facing annual overdrafts. As such, the future scenarios point not only to rising irrigation costs, but to deepening structural risks to the region's economy, employment base, and food security—underscoring the urgency of integrated water-efficiency targets and multi-scalar drought preparedness frameworks.

3.2 Current situation of river flood risk in the CARM

In the southeast of the Iberian Peninsula, specifically in the CARM, an increase in economic losses due to fluvial flooding has been observed over the past sixty years, despite the fact that the trend in the frequency of torrential rainfall events remains unclear in the Mediterranean region. This has been confirmed by (CEDEX, 2021) in its report on the impact of climate change on rainfall patterns in eastern Spain for the 1971–2000 period. However, according to CMIP6 ensemble maps in the Copernicus Interactive Climate Atlas, south-eastern Spain—including the Segura River basin that drains most of the CARM—shows a consistent intensification of the river-flood hazard component of the CLIMAAX River & Inland Floods workflow. The Atlas projects that the annual maximum one-day rainfall (Rx1day) will increase by $\approx 10\%$ in 2041–2070 under the intermediate SSP2-4.5 scenario and by 20–25% under the high-end SSP5-8.5 pathway, relative to the 1991–2020 baseline. Likewise, the frequency of very-wet days (R20mm index) is expected to nearly double by the late century in the high-emissions case, implying that cloudburst-type DANA events will occur more often and with greater spatial extent. In hydrological terms, these changes translate into shorter return periods for peak discharges: what is now a 1-in-50-year flow at key Segura gauges could occur every 20–25 years by mid-century, escalating the hazard module of the risk equation. When this heightened hazard intersects with the region's high exposure and with persistent socio-economic vulnerability, the overall fluvial-flood risk for CARM rises sharply, underscoring the need for integrated adaptation measures identified through the CLIMAAX CRA (Copernicus and ECMWF, 2025). However, it is necessary to emphasize the discrepancy between these results and those of (CEDEX, 2021), which, using high-resolution regional models, show that the future scenario is statistically significant towards a decrease in intense rainfall in the CARM. This invites the application of higher-resolution regional models in the CLIMAAX tool for a correct estimation of river flood hazard.

Preliminary results align with these findings, as shown in Figure 3-2. According to Gil-Guirado et al., 2019, the number of episodes capable of causing floods does not display a statistically significant trend. However, the ratio of affected municipalities or flood cases per episode has increased.

Figure 3-2 Evolution of the number of flood cases in the CARM. Source: Barriendos et al., 2019; Tuset et al., 2023.

This suggests that socio-economic growth—reflected in widespread, and in many cases unregulated, housing construction—and land-use planning models that fail to properly integrate flood risk are driving a growing exposure, and with it, increased damages. This is further evidenced by the rising number of exposed buildings in the Region of Murcia, according to cadastral data combined with the National Flood Hazard Mapping System (SNCZI) for return periods (RP) of 10, 100, and 500 years (Figure 3-3).

Figure 3-3 Evolution of exposed buildings in the CARM by Return Period (RP) (N=420,513 buildings). Source: MITECO, 2025.

From a land surface perspective, this increase in exposure, as measured using the 2018 CORINE Land Cover database (Copernicus, 2025), corresponds to approximately 46.77 km² affected by the 500-year RP, representing 10.9% of the CARM's artificial surface (Figure 3-4). The most worrying

figures correspond to RP10, with more than 11 km² affected, representing 2.6% of the artificial surface in the CARM.

Figure 3-4 Percentage of total surface area in the Region of Murcia (11,316 km²) (Left). Affected surface area and percentage of "Artificial Surfaces" (under each RP of the SNCZI) (Right). Source: Copernicus, 2025; MITECO, 2025.

In light of these reflections on the causes and consequences behind the rising—mainly economic—losses, and thus the overall risk, adaptation strategies in semi-arid areas like the CARM must urgently address the challenges of spatial planning and land management in order to achieve effective adaptation to projected climate change scenarios related to flood hazard.

3.3 Current situation of coastal flood risk in the CARM

Planning and preparation for the predicted climate change induced SLR is crucial for optimal adaptation of society and the economy in the CARM. This is especially true when considering the high levels of vulnerability and exposure of goods and services, as well as the high population density along the region's coasts. This phenomenon, driven by anthropogenic climate change (CC), threatens, among other things, frequent and/or permanent flooding, coastal erosion, and the loss of vital ecosystems. Furthermore, the regional economy, heavily dependent on coastal tourism and maritime activities, could suffer significant impacts. Therefore, anticipating these changes through adaptation and mitigation strategies is not only an essential preventive measure to protect lives and property, but also a strategic action to ensure the sustainability and resilience of the CARM in the face of future climate challenges. However, SLR projections face numerous sources of uncertainty, which hinder and limit sound coastal planning in the medium and long term. These sources of uncertainty come from five main components (Vousdoukas et al., 2018b): (1) the inclusion and interaction of different hydraulic components that model extreme sea level, (2) the underlying uncertainty in the digital elevation model (DEM), (3) flood defense information, (4) the assumptions behind the use of depth-damage functions that express vulnerability, and (5) different climate change projections. Uncertainties 2, 3, and 4 are the most important and introduce extreme dispersion in the different probabilistic scenarios. These additional biases, which do not support other climatic extremes, make correct planning difficult, since adaptation decisions are preferably based on specific solid and socioeconomic scenarios (Lincke and Hinkel, 2018).

A recent study (Tebaldi et al., 2021) concluded that by 2100, approximately 50% of the global coastline would experience at least once a year extreme coastal flooding events currently considered very unlikely (100-year return period under current conditions), even with warming below 1.5°C. At the societal level, SLR is expected to induce forced population displacement and huge economic losses on a global scale (Jones and O'Neill, 2016). With the global coastal population projected to exceed one billion people this century, SLR could become one of the most costly and

permanent future consequences of climate change, with direct impacts on populations (Hauer et al., 2021), commercial activities and services (Verschuur et al., 2023), the coastal real estate market (Murfin and Spiegel, 2020), aggregate economic losses (Lincke and Hinkel, 2018), cultural heritage (Sesana et al., 2021), and a significant impact on coastal ecosystems and landscapes (McNutt, 2013).

Regarding the expected socioeconomic impact of SLR, projections also face the uncertainty associated with different shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs) (Jones & O'Neill, 2016). This uncertainty, which also affects other extreme events associated with anthropogenic climate change (CC) (Changnon et al., 2000), is particularly relevant in the case of SRL (Kirezci et al., 2020). Unlike other risks such as droughts, the difference between an inaccurate estimate can lead to a location being categorized as fully affected (flooded under all conditions) or unaffected (not flooded). This is an added difficulty for decision-makers, as they must manage the territory with the uncertainty of taking measures that may never be necessary, or assume the risk of doing so (López-Martínez et al., 2017).

Recent literature indicates that extreme sea levels in Europe could rise by more than one meter by the end of this century, posing significant challenges for coastal communities. However, the benefit-adaptation relationship varies significantly, being more efficient in high-emission scenarios and strong socioeconomic growth (Vousdoukas et al., 2020).

Mediterranean sea level has shown significant increases in recent decades. Recent studies indicate that between 2000 and 2018, sea level in the Mediterranean region rose approximately 7 cm, a trend that exceeds the rates of increase observed during the 20th century (Calafat et al., 2022). Projections for the end of the 21st century vary depending on the greenhouse gas emissions scenario. According to (Vousdoukas et al., 2020), Mediterranean sea level is expected to rise between 0.79 m and 1.92 m under extreme high-emission scenarios. In addition to the average SLR, extreme events such as storm surges and storm surges are becoming more frequent and severe (Anzidei et al., 2024). Despite the significant expected impacts of SLR in Spain, the country does not consider SLR levels above 1 meter in its planning strategies by the end of this century (Vousdoukas et al., 2018a). In this situation, there is a risk of costly long-term adaptation, or of not having enough time to adapt if the SLR rate accelerates. In the context of the Spanish Mediterranean Coast, this issue takes on a crucial dimension due to the high population density, the economic value of infrastructure, and the ecological richness of its coasts (Estrela-Segrelles et al., 2021).

Additionally, the literature on the impact of SLR on the Spanish Mediterranean autonomous communities is scarce and scattered, with a significant gap for the provinces between Málaga and Castellón (Portillo Juan et al., 2022). This situation makes improvements urgently needed, enabling both the acquisition of a realistic current picture and the generation of future scenarios tailored to that reality.

The Copernicus Interactive Climate Atlas indicates that the *relative sea-level change* variable for the western Mediterranean—including the Murcian littoral—will rise by about 0.25–0.35 m by mid-century under SSP2-4.5 and by 0.45–0.55 m under SSP5-8.5, reaching 0.57 m and 0.79 m respectively by 2100 (baseline 1995-2014). Such vertical shifts, when fed into the CLIMAAX Coastal Floods workflow, amplify the *hazard* module by lowering the return period of extreme total water levels: a storm tide that today has a 1-in-100-year probability could occur every 20–30 years under the intermediate pathway and as often as once a decade under the high-end scenario. When this

rising hazard intersects with Murcia's high *exposure*—densely built tourist resorts, the Cartagena-Escombreras petro-industrial hub, and critical port and road links—and with existing *vulnerabilities* (subsiding reclaimed land, limited natural buffers), the overall coastal-flood risk escalates sharply, underscoring the urgency of shoreline-management plans and resilience investments identified in the CLIMAAX CRA. (Copernicus and ECMWF, 2025).

Regarding the CARM coastline, Martínez-Graña et al., (2018) carried out a high-resolution study for the Mar Menor coast where they obtained SLR (permanent occupation of the water sheet) ranges for the extreme emissions scenario of up to 0.92 meters, to which is added an extreme wave of 4.1 meters for the RP100. This would give rise to extreme events of permanent occupation of marine water for the land located below 0.92 meters and at least one coastal flooding in 100 years for the land located between 0.92 and 5.82 meters.

The coastline of the Region of Murcia (CARM) – only 274 km long but hosting a petrochemical hub, highly seasonal beach tourism, and 32% of the regional population – is already experiencing measurable impacts from coastal flooding that will be amplified by SLR and storm surge intensification.

According to 2023 data (Atlas Digital de las Áreas Urbanas de España, 2024), almost 490,000 inhabitants live in the eight coastal municipalities of the CARM. The sociodemographic conditions of these municipalities differ from the national average due to the economic dynamism and specialization in tourism functions of the study area (Gil-Guirado et al., 2022). The main demographic variables for 2023 (Atlas Digital de las Áreas Urbanas de España, 2024) speak for themselves: compared to a national municipal population density of 178 inhabitants/km² in the coastal municipalities of the CARM, this value is 524; the national average sex ratio is 117 women for every man, compared to 15 points less in the study area; while for the average Spanish municipality, the percentage of the population under 14 years of age compared to the total population is 9%, in the study area this value rises to 17%. Regarding the percentage of the population over 65 years of age, these values are 30% and 17% respectively; compared to a median municipal age of 49 years at the national level, this value drops to 41 years in the CARM coast. Finally, compared to a national average of 8% of the population not born in Spain, this figure rises to 23% in the study area. These figures reflect a demographically diverse population. However, these demographic considerations have not been considered so far in studies on the impact of the level at the regional level.

From a social perspective, the goal is to protect the most vulnerable coastal communities and ensure their resilience to climate change. The participation of local communities in the planning process will foster informed populations in the face of natural hazards, strengthening the collective capacity to respond to the challenges of climate change.

3.4 Current situation of Heatwaves risk in the CARM

The CARM has become increasingly exposed to extreme heatwaves that exceed both historical norms and human tolerance thresholds (Sherwood and Ramsay, 2023). Recent summers have broken records repeatedly: the heatwaves of 2003, 2012, 2015, 2018 and especially 2022–2023 produced maximum temperatures above 43 °C in Murcia city and surrounding areas, along with tropical nights where minima remained above 25–26 °C. Exposing about a million inhabitants to this risk.

The 2015 episode was the longest since at least 1975, spanning 26 days, while July 2022 brought unprecedented daily highs of 45.1 °C. The summer of 2023 was catalogued by AEMET as “extremely hot,” with anomalies exceeding +2.5 °C relative to the 1991–2020 climatological baseline. In 2024, although coastal areas were less directly affected, a surge in tropical nights was recorded along the Murcian coastline.

In this regard, Espín-Sánchez and Conesa-García (2021) identified an increase in the total number of heatwaves between 1950 and 2018 of 0.5 events/decade at the Alcantarilla station (Murcia) and 0.3 events/decade at the San Javier station (Figure 3-5). Since 2013, there has been a marked increase in the number of events, raising this ratio to approximately 1 event/decade. According to these authors, the average heatwave sequence duration increased by around 2 days every 10 years at both stations. The temporal trend of these extremely hot sequences has shown a high correlation with the evolution of the East Atlantic Index (EAI), particularly in Mediterranean coastal areas like San Javier (Kendall correlation > 0.53; p-value < 0.05) (Espín-Sánchez and Conesa-García, 2021) (Figure 3-5).

Figure 3-5 Map of Temporal Trends in the Frequency (EHF_HWF) and Number (EHF_HWN) of Heatwaves per Decade in Spain (1950–2016). For the CARM, the observed trend is shown for the stations of Alcantarilla and San Javier. Source: Espín-Sánchez and Conesa-García (2021).

Future projections reinforce this risk. According to the Copernicus Climate Atlas (Copernicus and ECMWF, 2025), the CARM will experience a marked rise in the number of tropical nights and extremely hot days under all emissions scenarios. Between 2041 and 2070, the duration of consecutive tropical nights is expected to increase by 5–10 days per year under SSP2-4.5, and by 12–18 days under SSP5-8.5. Heat stress indices, such as the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI), similarly project more frequent days above critical comfort thresholds. These changes imply more persistent physiological stress, reduced labour productivity, and accelerated degradation of both urban and rural systems.

3.5 Most Relevant Risk Selection

Based on the hazard screening and the specific context of the Region of Murcia (CARM), the Climate Risk Assessment (CRA) will prioritise this most relevant risk: Agricultural Droughts, River and Coastal Floods, and Heatwaves. The forthcoming analyses will focus on these workflows given their pertinence to the region’s semi-arid climate, hydro-climatic extremes, and socio-economic characteristics.

The agricultural drought is particularly critical for the CARM, where 46% of cultivated land is irrigated and agri-food exports exceed €6,900 million annually. Exposure is dominated by high-value, water-intensive crops and a dense agro-industrial sector, while vulnerability concentrates in smallholders, ageing farming populations and groundwater-dependent rural communities. River and coastal floods represent another major risk: torrential rainfall and flash floods affect the Segura basin and its urban areas, while 32% of the regional population and strategic assets are located along the 274 km coastline exposed to storm surges and sea-level rise. Vulnerability is heightened in poorly planned peri-urban settlements, socio-economically disadvantaged neighbourhoods and coastal communities reliant on seasonal tourism. Heatwaves add a third dimension of risk, with intensifying extremes and urban heat islands in Murcia, Cartagena and other dense municipalities. Elderly residents, children, outdoor workers and low-income households are particularly exposed, and critical infrastructure such as hospitals, schools and energy systems face recurrent stress during extreme events.

4 REGMURCIA CLIMAAX Project Work Plan

The workplan concisely includes both technical tasks and dissemination activities.

Phase 1: Application of the CLIMAAX Common Methodology (Months 1–6):

Activities:

- Prepare a reference document outlining context and criteria.
- Identify key climate risks for Murcia.
- Utilize the CLIMAAX toolbox for initial risk assessment.
- Contact with key stakeholders to present the project.
- Create a page on the “murcianatural” website and feed with results.
- Initiate project dissemination activities
- Attend the CLIMAAX workshop in Barcelona.

Deliverable 1: Comprehensive risk assessment report.

Phase 2: Refinement Using Local Data (Months 7–16):

Activities:

- Conduct technical meetings to refine assessments from Phase 1.
- Incorporate high-resolution local data to enhance accuracy.
- Develop technical studies or high-resolution maps using GIS data for precise impact estimation.
- Continue working on dissemination activities.
- Feed the page of “murcianatural” and MAR research group’s websites with results.

Deliverable 2: Refined multi-risk assessment.

Phase 3: Exploration of Adaptation Options (Months 17–22):

Activities:

- Conduct participatory workshops with stakeholders to present and discuss results.
- Develop a catalog of adaptation measures tailored to address risks, incorporating workshop insights.
- Prepare a summary document with actionable steps and sectorial plans, including prioritized measures, timelines, responsibilities, and budgets.
- Publication of the results.
- Attend the CLIMAAX workshop in Brussels.

Deliverable 3: Sector-specific adaptation action plans enhancing the Regional Strategy.

Phase 1 of the REGMURCIA CLIMAAX project will be centred on the screening and preliminary analysis of priority climate hazards. Phases 2 and 3 will build upon the foundations established during the Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment. These subsequent phases aim to refine the technical diagnosis and support the development of region-specific, stakeholder-led adaptation pathways. The overarching goal is to advance from initial risk identification to actionable and institutionally anchored adaptation planning.

5 Scoping Insights

The screening suggests that agricultural drought stands out as the most critical risk, with intensifying hazards across meteorological, hydrological and agricultural dimensions. Exposure is particularly high given the large share of irrigated, high-value crops and the density of agro-industry, while vulnerabilities concentrate in smallholders, ageing farmers and aquifers already under stress. River floods appear to be driven more by growth in exposure than by changes in hazard. Expanding peri-urban areas and road networks intersecting ephemeral channels increase the potential for losses, while current projections remain inconsistent: CEDEX analyses point to stable or declining intensities, whereas CMIP6 and Atlas data suggest an increase. Planning performance and drainage capacity will be decisive factors in determining real impacts.

Coastal floods and sea-level rise represent another high-priority concern. Along a short but heavily occupied coastline, including tourism hubs and the Cartagena–Escombreras industrial complex, relative sea-level rise reduces return periods for extreme events. The most relevant uncertainties are not global projections but local determinants such as DEM accuracy, the condition and crest levels of coastal defenses, and the choice of depth–damage functions.

Heatwaves are already increasing in frequency and duration, with more tropical nights observed. Their main consequences fall on public health, productivity and energy demand, particularly within the urban heat islands of Murcia and Cartagena and among elderly populations and outdoor workers.

From this screening, several potential hotspots emerge: the Segura floodplain and tributary ramblas crossing peri-urban growth areas in Murcia, Lorca and Cartagena; the low-lying fringes of the Mar Menor and La Manga; the petro-industrial shore at Cartagena–Escombreras; irrigated belts highly sensitive to water costs and dependent on transfers and desalination; and dense urban neighbourhoods where canopy cover is limited and social vulnerability is high.

For the correct development of the project, it will be necessary more robust data and methods. For floods, this means updated IDF curves, land-use and permeability layers, and reliable information on the height and condition of flood defenses. For the coast, harmonised LiDAR/DTM, an inventory of defenses and their crest levels, and local joint probability data for surge and waves will be essential. Drought analysis needs improved data on groundwater abstractions, farm-level water cost–yield functions, and the operational boundaries of reuse and desalination. Heat-related assessments require higher-resolution canopy and impervious surface maps, building typologies, and health micro-data to capture social vulnerability.

Governance aspects should also be considered, including decision thresholds and acceptable-risk levels for different sectors, as well as financeability under ERDF, LIFE, CAP, NextGen and green bond frameworks.

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